

Original Research

Unveiling Drivers of Environmental Disclosure in Mining: Performance, Profitability, and Size

Indah Maulidiah¹
Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Swadaya Gunung Jati, Cirebon,
Indonesia

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Abstract

This study analyzes the variables influencing environmental disclosure in companies by focusing on company size, profitability, and environmental performance. When descriptive statistical analysis was performed on a sample of 60 companies, the average environmental disclosure score was 0.3246, suggesting that transparency is still lacking and needs to be improved. Data normality was tested using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov method, and no issues of heteroscedasticity were found. The results show that the level of environmental disclosure is negatively influenced by environmental performance, as measured by the PROPER score. While company size, determined by taking the logarithm of total assets, has a positive impact, profitability, as indicated by Return on Assets (ROA), also exhibits a negative effect. According to the report, greater environmental effects are typically associated to larger companies. According to multiple regression analysis, the variable studied only explains 15.2% of the variation in environmental disclosure, indicating that there may be more factors that have not yet been studied. According to these findings, corporate environmental disclosure is crucial for improving a company's reputation and reducing the information gap between stakeholders and companies.

Keywords: Company size, Environmental disclosure, Environmental performance, Profitability.

¹ Corresponding author's Email: idarosnidah@ugj.ac.id

Introduction

In today's rapidly evolving global economy, environmental issues have become a major concern in many countries, including Indonesia. The mining sector, which heavily relies on the depletion of natural resources, has a substantial effect on social welfare, economic development, and environmental sustainability (Yousefian et al., 2023). Mining activities frequently result in water and air pollution as well as land degradation.

Evidence suggests that many companies prioritize financial gain over environmental responsibility. A concrete example of this issue is illegal mining activity in Sumber Sari Village, Loa Kulu District, East Kalimantan, which has caused ecological and social harm directly impacting the local community (Farauqi et al., 2024). Companies that are committed to Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) values can enhance their legitimacy and stakeholder appeal by emphasizing the importance of transparent environmental information as a form of public accountability and a legitimacy strategy (Silvia & Guo, 2024).

As a response to environmental concerns, the Indonesian government requires mining companies to implement social and environmental responsibilities, as stipulated in Government Regulation No. 47 of 2012 (PP No. 47, 2012). This requirement is further strengthened by directives issued by Regulatory Body for Financial Services (OJK), such as Regulation No. 51 of 2017 and Circular Letter No. 16/SEOJK.04/2021, which aim to encourage greater transparency in sustainability reporting (Otoritas Jasa Keuangan Nomor 51 /POJK.03/2017, 2017; Surat Edaran Otoritas Jasa Keuangan Nomor 16/SEOJK.04/2021, 2021). The impact of these regulations is reflected in the increased ESG scores in the mining sector, rising from 36% in 2021 to 63.78% in 2023 (Fadlillah, 2024). Environmental disclosure has become a key mechanism encouraging companies to manage their environmental impact more (Istiqomah & Wahyuningrum, 2020). Collaboration among all stakeholders is essential to support ESG implementation, achieve sustainable development goals, and address global challenges (Almeyda & Darmansyah, 2019; Machmuddah & Wardhani, 2020; Miklosik et al., 2021).

However, despite the ongoing development of regulations and ESG initiatives, previous studies have reported inconsistent findings regarding the factors influencing environmental disclosure. Some studies found that environmental performance, profitability, and company size significantly affect environmental disclosure (Digdowiseiso et al., 2022; Istiqomah & Wahyuningrum, 2020; Yin et al., 2019), while others reported contrasting results (Purwanto & Nugroho, 2020; Siregar & Kusumawardhani, 2023; Wahyuningrum et al., 2022). These inconsistencies indicate a research gap that requires further investigation.

Furthermore, an analysis of annual reports from coal mining sub-sector companies in Indonesia, along with data from the Central Bureau of Statistics (Badan Pusat Statistik, 2025) reveals fluctuations in production and sales volumes during the 2021–2023 period. Compliance with the environmental reporting criteria of the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) is still below ideal, even though several businesses have declared excellent profitability. Many companies provide only basic information without detailing their

environmental impacts. This may influence stakeholders' perceptions of the companies' commitment to sustainability (Du Toit, 2024).

Based on the background mentioned above, the main issue identified is the uncertainty regarding which factors most significantly influence environmental disclosure in mining companies, particularly in the coal sub-sector. In addition, the inconsistency of previous research findings and the evolving business landscape highlight the need to revisit the determinants of environmental disclosure.

Therefore, this research is meant to examine the impact of environmental performance, profitability, and company size on the level of environmental disclosure in coal mining companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX). The focus is directed toward companies with high environmental reporting obligations due to the nature of their operations, which are directly linked to natural resource exploitation. This study contributes theoretically by re-examining the relevance of legitimacy and signaling theories in the context of developing countries, particularly Indonesia's mining industry, which has institutional, regulatory, and social pressure characteristics that differ from those of developed countries. It also contributes theoretically to the development of environmental accounting literature and offers practical recommendations for improving corporate transparency and accountability in managing environmental impacts. Thus, this research is not merely replicative but also exploratory in nature, challenging the limitations of established theoretical frameworks.

Although ESG issues are gaining increasing importance in Indonesia, empirical studies specifically addressing the coal mining sub-sector remain limited (Lestari et al., 2025). Thus, this research provides more focused empirical evidence to support the development of targeted policies and oversight for sectors with high environmental impact.

Theoretical Review and Hypothesis Framework

Legitimacy Theory

Legitimacy theory was introduced by Dowling & Pfeffer (1975) as an important framework for understanding organizational behavior and its existence in society. A company is considered legitimate if its goals and actions are aligned with prevailing social values and norms. Legitimacy represents public acceptance of a company's existence (Solikhah et al., 2020), which is a crucial factor in maintaining business sustainability. Companies are expected to demonstrate social accountability by acting responsibly to fulfill the expectations of investors and society (Akhter et al., 2023). Therefore, environmental information disclosure narrows the legitimacy gap between corporate actions and societal expectations (Wahyuningrum et al., 2022).

Signaling Theory

Signaling Theory, introduced by Spence (1973), explains that information holders (companies) send signals to information recipients (investors or other interested parties) to reduce information asymmetry. Within the context of environmental disclosure, positive signals in environmental transparency indicate good corporate quality (Brigham

& Houston, 2019). Comprehensive disclosure allows companies to demonstrate responsibility and sustainable performance to the public (Hassan et al., 2020). These signals also cover sustainability, financial stability, and social awareness (López-Santamaría et al., 2021).

Environmental Disclosure

According to (Maharani et al., 2024; Solikhah & Maulina, 2021; Suratno et al., 2007), environmental disclosure refers to the disclosure of environmental-related information in a company's annual report. Companies disclose their environmental performance across various components to generate a positive public response and gain legitimacy for their operations. The checklist used to measure environmental disclosure is derived from the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) 4.0 indicators.

Environmental Performance

One definition of environmental performance is the capacity of an environmental management system to regulate the environmental components of a business (Ikhsan, 2009). The PROPER rating and the application of environmental management systems are two ways that Indonesia's environmental performance may be evaluated. The Ministry of Environment offers a ranking system called PROPER that shows how well a company performs regarding the environment. Accordingly, businesses with higher PROPER ratings are often better equipped to disclose important environmental information than those with lower ratings (Wahyuningrum et al., 2020).

Profitability

According to Brigham & Houston (2019), profitability reflects the net results of a company's operational activities within a given period. It indicates a company's ability to generate profits and the effectiveness of its management. Higher profitability is often associated with greater disclosure of social responsibility. Miranatha & Wirawati (2021) further state that profitability can be assessed using financial ratios to analyze a company's financial position, operating results, and profitability levels. This information helps stakeholders in decision-making. Profitability is measured using the return on assets (ROA) indicator.

Company Size

According to Brigham & Houston (2019), company size refers to the scale of a company, which can be classified in several ways, including total revenue, total assets, and total equity. Larger companies tend to maintain stability and performance by continuously improving their operations. They are also considered more competitive in capital markets and more capable of generating profits. Moreover, large companies often have better control mechanisms, resulting in stronger economic performance (Andriana & Anisykurlillah, 2019).

The Influence of Environmental Performance on Environmental Disclosure

Environmental performance can provide varied financial benefits across companies. According to signaling theory, environmental responsibility asserts that companies can manage their business to avoid causing environmental damage. Since environmentally sensitive industries have negative impacts on the environment, companies gain more significant financial benefits when they achieve higher environmental performance, such as sustainability advantages and consistent business performance. Studies by (Digdowiseiso et al., 2022) and (Siregar & Kusumawardhani, 2023) show that environmental performance significantly affects environmental disclosure. Based on the above, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H₁: Environmental performance positively influences the extent of environmental disclosure.

The Influence of Profitability on Environmental Disclosure

Legitimacy theory states that businesses are under social pressure to solve environmental issues. Firms with greater profitability are generally more capable of responding to these demands, as they possess the necessary resources to facilitate environmental disclosure more effectively than less profitable firms. Research conducted by (Purwanto & Nugroho, 2020; Putra, 2021; Siregar & Kusumawardhani, 2023) supports the existence of a link between profitability and environmental disclosure. Based on this rationale, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H₂: Profitability positively influences the extent of environmental disclosure.

The Influence of Company Size on Environmental Disclosure

Company size represents the overall scale of a business and can be assessed through indicators such as total assets, total sales, or their respective averages. Research by (Istiqomah & Wahyuningrum, 2020; Purwanto & Nugroho, 2020) suggests that larger firms tend to disclose more environmental information. This implies that companies with greater assets are more likely to report on their environmental initiatives. As a company grows, its environmental footprint also expands, encouraging broader disclosure to uphold legitimacy and demonstrate accountability to the public. This reasoning leads to the formulation of the hypothesis below:

H₃: Company size positively influences the extent of environmental disclosure.

Figure 1. Hypothesis Framework

Research Method

A descriptive quantitative research approach was employed for this study. (Fauzi, 2019) defines quantitative research as being founded on numerical data that is used to analyze observed phenomena, which characteristically involves information in a numerical format. This study is based on secondary data gathered from Financial Reports, Annual Reports, and Sustainability Reports for mining companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange during 2019-2023. The required documents were retrieved from the individual company websites and the official website of the Indonesia Stock Exchange. A purposive sampling method was applied to select the sample.

The sample selection criteria for this research, derived from the preceding explanation, are detailed in the subsequent table.

Table 1. Sample Selection Criteria

Criteria	Total
Population of mining companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2019 – 2023	34
Mining companies that did not participate in PROPER in 2019 – 2023	16
Mining companies that did not publish financial reports and annual reports in 2019 – 2023	6
Total mining companies that meet the criteria	12
Total Sample (n x research period)	60

The sample in this study consisted of 60 mining companies listed on the IDX 2019-2023 and met the sample selection criteria.

Variable Operationalization

Environmental disclosure, the dependent variable in this study, is assessed with a checklist based on the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) version 4.0, which includes 117 indicators across economic, environmental, and social aspects. A content analysis of corporate annual and sustainability reports was performed to conduct the evaluation. A score of 1 was assigned to every disclosed item, whereas undisclosed items were given a score of 0. The final score was calculated by dividing the sum of disclosed items by the 117 total possible indicators, with the outcome presented as a percentage.

The following is the formula used:

$$\text{Environmental Disclosure} = \frac{\Sigma X}{n} \quad (1)$$

ΣX Total items disclosed by the company

n Total items of GRI standar environmental indicators

Environmental performance assesses a company's ability to create positive value for its environment (Alifaliyudin & Purbasari, 2024). The relationship between the company and the environment is determined by the PROPER score it receives, which is then categorized into colors defined by the Ministry of Environment and Forestry (MENLHK). The PROPER performance rating system ranks companies into five colors, scored from lowest to highest: 1 for black (very poor), 2 for red (poor), 3 for blue (fair), 4 for green (good), and the highest is gold (excellent). Profitability is defined as a company's ability to generate profit from all capital employed in the business (Siregar & Kusumawardhani, 2023).

Profitability is defined as a company's capacity to generate profits from its operations. Return on assets (ROA) is a standard metric for this.

$$ROA = \frac{\text{Net profit after tax}}{\text{Total assets}} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

The increased public attention and stakeholder demands placed on larger corporations compel them to seek legitimacy and foster a positive public perception through social and environmental reporting (Antara et al., 2020). Metrics such as total assets, sales, the number of employees, and market capitalization are used to evaluate a company's size. A company's size is additionally affected by its financial results.

To measure the company size variable, this study uses the following formula:

$$\text{Size} = \text{Ln}(\text{Total assets}) \quad (3)$$

Data Analysis Technique and Methods

Descriptive Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistical analysis is a technique that provides an overview of the data used and describes the variables in this study. This analysis only offers a summary or description of the data for each variable, which includes minimum and maximum values, mean, and standard deviation (Ghozali, 2018).

Classical Assumption Test

Normality Test

The normality test aims to determine whether the variables used in this study follow a normal distribution. The One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test is used for this purpose. If the significance value is greater than $\alpha = 0.05$, the data are normally distributed. Conversely, if the significance value is less than $\alpha = 0.05$, the data are not normally distributed.

Multicollinearity Test

The multicollinearity test is performed to ensure the independent variables in a regression model are not significantly intercorrelated. Multicollinearity is considered absent when the tolerance value is above 0.1, and the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) is under 10. In contrast, the potential for multicollinearity arises if the tolerance value is less than 0.1 and the VIF is greater than 10.

Autocorrelation Test

The autocorrelation test determines whether a correlation exists between residuals at time t and those at time $t-1$ in a regression model. The Durbin-Watson (D-W) statistic is employed to detect the presence of autocorrelation. A D-W value below -2 suggests positive autocorrelation, a value between -2 and 2 indicates no autocorrelation and a value above 2 signifies negative autocorrelation.

Heteroscedasticity Test

The purpose of the heteroscedasticity test is to assess whether the variance of residuals is consistent across all observations in the regression model. An ideal regression model should exhibit homoscedasticity, meaning the residuals have equal variance and should not show signs of heteroscedasticity (Ghozali, 2018). This can be evaluated using a scatterplot, where the pattern of data points spread evenly above and below the Y-axis at the value of 0 helps indicate whether heteroscedasticity is present or absent.

Multiple Linear Analysis

In this study, hypothesis testing is conducted using multiple linear regression analysis, which determines the direction and extent to which the independent variables influence the dependent variable.

The regression equation is as follows:

$$ED = \alpha + \beta_1 EP + \beta_2 P + \beta_3 CS + e \quad (4)$$

<i>ED</i>	Environmental Disclosure
α	Constant
β	Regression Coefficient
<i>EP</i>	Environmental Performance
<i>P</i>	Profitability
<i>CS</i>	Company Size
<i>e</i>	Error

Hypothesis Test

Partial Test (Statistical Test t)

The degree to which a single independent variable (X) contributes to explaining the dependent variable (Y) is assessed using the t-test. A significance threshold of 0.05 ($\alpha = 5\%$) is used for the test, and the following criteria are used for making decisions:

- A hypothesis is accepted if the significance value is less than 0.05, which shows that there is a significant relationship between the independent variable (X) and the dependent variable (Y).
- The hypothesis is rejected if the significance value exceeds 0.05, demonstrating that there is no discernible relationship between the independent variable (X) and the dependent variable (Y).

Simultaneous Test (F Statistical Test)

According to (Ghozali, 2018), the F-statistical test assesses the Goodness of Fit of a regression model. It determines whether the independent variables collectively have a significant effect on the dependent variable. The criteria for decision-making are as follows:

- If the significance value is greater than 0.05, the model is not suitable for testing.
- If the significance value is less than 0.05, the model is appropriate and statistically valid for testing.

Coefficient of Determination Analysis

The degree to which the regression model captures the variability in the dependent variable is indicated by the coefficient of determination (R^2). The range of R^2 values is 0 to 1. While a number nearer 1 indicates that the model can explain almost all of the variance, offering significant predictive potential, a lower R^2 value indicates that the

independent variables only explain a tiny percentage of the variation in the dependent variable (Ghozali, 2018).

Results and Discussion

Descriptive Analysis

The output of the descriptive statistical analysis processed using SPSS Statistics 29 presents the mean, minimum, maximum, and standard deviation values for each research variable.

Table 2. Descriptive Analysis Results

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Environmental Performance	60	.00	5.00	3.4333	1.61944
Profitability	60	-.10	.62	.1911	.17836
Company Size	60	19.89	32.76	29.3370	3.14636
Environmental Disclosure	60	.00	1.00	.3246	.36525
Valid N (listwise)	60				

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistical results for each variable in this study, based on a sample size (N) of 60. PT. Alamtri Resources Indonesia Tbk. and PT. Bukit Asam Tbk. achieved the highest environmental performance score of 5.00, having received the gold PROPER rating for five consecutive years. The average environmental performance score was 3.4333, with a standard deviation of 1.61944, indicating that the environmental performance data were relatively homogeneous. Profitability, measured by Return on Assets (ROA), had a mean value of 0.1911 with a standard deviation of 0.17836. According to Andriana and Anisykurlillah (2019), the data distribution is considered favorable when the mean exceeds the standard deviation. The average company size, assessed by the natural logarithm of total assets, was 29.3370 with a standard deviation of 3.14636, implying that larger companies tend to have a greater environmental impact. Lastly, the Environmental Disclosure variable recorded a mean value of 0.3246 and a standard deviation of 0.36525. Since the standard deviation is higher than the mean, it suggests a relatively high level of data dispersion, indicating an inconsistency in environmental disclosure practices among the sampled companies.

Classical Assumption Test

Normality Test

Based on the table 3, the Asymp. Sig. value is 0.200 with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$. Since the Asymp. Sig. value is greater than the significance level ($0.200 > 0.05$), it can be concluded that the null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted. This indicates that the residuals are normally distributed.

Table 3. Normality Test with *Kolmogorov-Smirnov*
 One Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		30
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	.41685505
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.085
	Positive	.085
	Negative	-.084
Test Statistic		.085
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200 ^{c,d}
a. Test distribution is Normal.		
b. Calculated from data.		
c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.		
d. This is all lower bound of the true significance.		

Multicollinearity Test

Table 4. Multicollinearity Test Results
 Coefficients^a

Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)		
	Environmental Performance	.801	1.249
	Profitability	.996	1.005
	Company Size	.803	1.245
a. Dependent Variable: Environmental Disclosure			

Based on Table 4, the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values for environmental performance, profitability, and company size are 1.249, 1.005, and 1.245, respectively (each within the acceptable range of 1 to 10). The tolerance values are also greater than 0.1: 0.801, 0.996, and 0.803, respectively. Therefore, the model is free from multicollinearity issues.

Autocorrelation Test

Table 5. Autocorrelation Test with *Durbin-Watson*
 Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.442 ^a	.195	.152	.33632	1.996
a. Predictors:(Constant), Company Size, Profitability, Environmental Performance					
b. Dependent Variable: Environmental Disclosure					

As seen in Table 5 above, the Durbin-Watson value is 1.996, which lies between -2 and +2. Therefore, this regression model does not exhibit autocorrelation.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Figure 2. Heteroscedasticity Test with Scatterplot

An examination of the scatterplot in Figure 2 indicates a random distribution of data points with no evident structure, positioned both above and below the Y-axis's zero mark. As a result, the regression model is deemed to be unaffected by heteroscedasticity.

Multiple Linear Analysis

Table 6. Multiple Linear Regression Test Coefficient^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	-.859	.426		-2.017	.048
	Environmental Performance	.049	.030	.219	1.633	.108
	Profitability	-.029	.246	-.014	-.118	.907
	Company Size	.035	.016	.299	2.238	.029

a. Dependent Variable: Environmental Disclosure

Source: SPSS Output, 2023

$$ED = \alpha + \beta_1 EP + \beta_2 P + \beta_3 CS + e$$

$$ED = -0.859 + 0.049 - 0.029 + 0.035 + e$$

Table 6 shows that the constant value (a) is -0.859. This indicates that if all independent variables remain constant, the level of environmental disclosure would be -0.859. The variables of environmental performance and company size have positive regression coefficients of 0.049 and 0.035, respectively. This means that an increase in each of these variables will increase the dependent variable (environmental disclosure) by the value of each coefficient, indicating a direct relationship. In contrast, the profitability variable has a negative regression coefficient of -0.029, indicating that an increase in profitability will reduce the environmental disclosure level by 0.029, showing an inverse relationship.

Hypothesis Test

Partial Test (T-Test)

To assess the specific impact of each independent variable, namely environmental performance, profitability, and company size on the dependent variable of environmental disclosure, a partial test was conducted. The outcomes of the hypothesis tests, processed with SPSS Statistics 29, are shown in the following section:

Table 7. Partial Test Results (t-test)
Coefficient^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	-.859	.426		-2.017	.048
	Environmental Performance	.049	.030	.219	1.633	.108
	Profitability	-.029	.246	-.014	-.118	.907
	Company Size	.035	.016	.299	2.238	.029
a. Dependent Variable: Environmental Disclosure						

Source: SPSS Output, 2023

Based on Table 7 above, the partial test results reveal each independent variable's influence on the dependent variable. The interpretations of the t-test are as follows:

The Influence of Environmental Performance on Environmental Disclosure

The analysis indicates that environmental performance, as evaluated by the PROPER score, does not significantly affect environmental disclosure. This conclusion is supported by a significance value of 0.108 above the 0.05 threshold. Additionally, the computed t-value of 1.633 is lower than the critical t-table value of 2.003 ($t(\alpha/2; n-k-1) = t(0.025; 56)$), which results in the rejection of the hypothesis for variable X1.

This result suggests that environmental performance (X1) has no significant partial influence on Environmental Disclosure (Y). In other words, an increase or decrease in environmental performance does not necessarily lead to changes in environmental disclosure.

Based on the research data, several companies did not receive a PROPER rating, including PT Baramulti Suksessarana Tbk. in 2020, PT Golden Energy Mines Tbk. in 2019, PT Indika Energy Tbk. in 2022, PT Dana Brata Luhur Tbk. in both 2019 and 2020, and PT Sumber Global Energy Tbk. in 2019, 2020, 2022, and 2023. For companies without a PROPER rating, their value is counted as zero. Consequently, the Environmental Performance (X1) variable does not influence Environmental Disclosure (Y).

These findings align with prior studies by Purwanto & Nugroho (2020) and Maulana et al. (2021), which also found that Environmental Performance does not significantly affect Environmental Disclosure.

The Influence of Profitability on Environmental Disclosure

Profitability, measured by Return on Assets (ROA), does not significantly affect environmental disclosure. This is evidenced by the significance value of 0.907, which exceeds the threshold of 0.05. Based on the t-table value at $t(\alpha/2; n-k-1) = t(0.025; 56) = 2.003$, the calculated t-value is -0.118, which is less than the t-table value ($-0.118 < 2.003$). Therefore, the hypothesis for X2 is rejected.

From the calculation results, it can be concluded that there is no significant partial effect of profitability (X2) on environmental disclosure (Y). Based on the research data, four companies experienced negative profitability or financial losses, including PT Indika Energy Tbk (2020), PT Bumi Resources Tbk (2020), PT Golden Eagle Energi Tbk (2020), and PT Dana Brata Luhur Tbk (2019). As a result, the profitability variable (X2) does not significantly influence the level of environmental disclosure (Y).

This finding is in line with studies by (Ardi & Yulianto, 2020; Dewi, 2019; Siregar & Kusumawardhani, 2023; Wahyuningrum et al., 2022), which identified a negative correlation between profitability and environmental disclosure. These results also align with the legitimacy theory, which suggests that higher profitability may lead companies to reduce the level of information disclosed. The rationale is that highly profitable firms are already considered legitimate and attractive to investors, thus reducing the pressure to disclose additional environmental information.

The Influence of Company Size on Environmental Disclosure

Company size (SIZE) significantly influences the disclosure of corporate social responsibility (CSR). This is demonstrated by a significance value of 0.029, which is below the 0.05 significance level. Using the t-table value of $t(\alpha/2; n-k-1) = t(0.025; 56) = 2.003$, the computed t-value is 2.238, exceeding the critical value ($2.238 > 2.003$). Consequently, the hypothesis for variable X3 is accepted.

Based on these results, it can be concluded that there is a significant partial relationship between firm size (X3) and environmental disclosure (Y). This means that changes in company size are associated with corresponding changes in the extent of environmental disclosure. In this study, the average company size among the 12 sampled companies measured using the natural logarithm of total assets was 29.34%. Hence, company size (X3) influenced environmental disclosure (Y).

These findings align with previous research by (Antara et al., 2020; Istiqomah & Wahyuningrum, 2020; Purwanto & Nugroho, 2020; Siregar & Kusumawardhani, 2023), which confirmed that company size is a significant determinant of environmental disclosure.

Moreover, the study reveals that only company size significantly affects environmental disclosure. This supports the legitimacy theory, which posits that larger companies face greater societal and regulatory pressures to enhance transparency (Suchman, 1995). In contrast, environmental performance and profitability variables did not show significant influence. This may be attributed to contextual factors in Indonesia's mining industry, where the absence of detailed implementation guidelines and weak capacity-building initiatives hinder consistent reporting compliance, especially in developing countries (Pratama et al., 2025).

Additionally, many companies do not regularly receive PROPER evaluations, and sustainability reports tend to be symbolic rather than reflective of substantive accountability (López-Santamaría et al., 2021). Highly profitable companies often focus their disclosures on mandatory financial aspects, neglecting voluntary environmental reporting (Ardi & Yulianto, 2020). This illustrates a reactive disclosure pattern, where companies respond mainly to external pressure rather than adopting a proactive sustainability strategy (Ali et al., 2022).

Subsequent studies are recommended to incorporate contextual variables such as stakeholder pressure, corporate governance, and government policy to serve as a foundation for developing more comprehensive research models on environmental disclosure dynamics in the future.

Simultaneous Test (F-Test)

The F-test was utilized to investigate the joint effect of environmental performance, profitability, and company size on environmental disclosure. The purpose of this test is to ascertain, at an alpha level of 0.05, whether the independent variables in aggregate significantly influence the dependent variable. The outcomes of the F-test are displayed in the subsequent table.

Table 8. Simultaneous Test Results (F-Test)
ANOVA^a

	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.537	3	.512	4.529	.007 ^b
	Residual	6.334	56	.113		
	Total	7.871	59			
a. Dependent Variable: Environmental Disclosure						
b. Predictors:(Constant), Company Size, Profitability, Environmental Performance						

According to Table 8, the F-test significance value is 0.007, below the 0.05 significance level. Furthermore, the calculated F-value of 4.529 is higher than the critical

F-table value of 2.77. As explained by Ghozali (2018), the Goodness of Fit test evaluates how well the regression model fits the data and determines if all independent variables collectively have a significant effect on the dependent variable.

Given that the significance level is below 0.05 ($0.007 < 0.05$) and the F-value is greater than the F-table value ($4.529 > 2.77$), the regression model is deemed appropriate for explaining variations in the dependent variable using the specified independent variables.

In conclusion, environmental performance (PROPER), profitability (ROA), and firm size (SIZE) collectively have a statistically significant effect on environmental disclosure.

Coefficient of Determination Analysis

The coefficient of determination (R^2) indicates the degree to which the regression model captures the variability in the dependent variable. The results of this calculation are presented in the following table:

Table 9. Coefficient of Determination (Adjusted R^2)
 Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.442 ^a	.195	.152	.33632	1.996
a. Predictors:(Constant), Company Size, Profitability, Environmental Performance					
b. Dependent Variable: Environmental Disclosure					

Based on Table 9, the coefficient of determination is indicated in the Adjusted R Square column, which shows a value of $R^2 = 0.152$. This means that the independent variables environmental performance (PROPER), profitability (ROA), and company size explain 15.2% of the variance in the dependent variable, environmental disclosure. The remaining 84.8% is influenced by other factors not examined in this study.

Although the regression model shows that only company size significantly affects environmental disclosure ($p = 0.029$), the relatively low R^2 value of 15.2% indicates that the independent variables used in this study explain only a small portion of the variation in environmental disclosure. Therefore, despite the low adjusted R^2 , the statistical significance of variables such as firm size suggests a consistent influence on environmental disclosure.

In this context, the low adjusted R^2 does not diminish the importance of these findings; rather, it implies that other factors should be considered in future models (Dewayani & Ratnadi, 2021).

Conclusion

Applying a quantitative method with statistical analysis, this study empirically examines the influence of environmental performance, profitability, and company size on environmental disclosure for a sample of 60 mining companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX). This topic is highly relevant given the growing global emphasis

on accountability and environmental sustainability, particularly in the resource-intensive mining sector.

The analysis results indicate that only company size positively affects environmental disclosure, whereas environmental performance and profitability do not have significant impacts. This finding suggests that larger companies are more likely to be transparent due to stronger public scrutiny and regulatory pressure. Conversely, the insignificant influence of profitability and environmental performance implies that disclosure is not always driven by financial outcomes or environmental achievements.

Although the model's predictive ability is limited, which has an Adjusted R^2 of only 15.2%, this research still offers meaningful insights by highlighting company size as a dominant factor influencing environmental disclosure and underscoring the limitations of PROPER and ROA as predictors (Akhter et al., 2023). Furthermore, these results confirm that disclosure practices in developing countries like Indonesia remain strongly shaped by institutional pressures, social factors, and companies' internal resource capacities (Pikri et al., 2023). Therefore, policy and regulatory reinforcement is necessary, especially to encourage environmental transparency among smaller companies or those with high profitability that currently lack strong incentives to disclose environmental information.

Overall, the scientific contribution of this research lies in providing relevant empirical evidence and stimulating discussion about the factors affecting environmental disclosure in the mining sector. This can serve as a foundation for developing more comprehensive research models in the future. Subsequent studies are recommended to incorporate additional variables such as board structure, audit committee effectiveness, stakeholder pressure, media exposure, and the presence of sustainability assurance. Qualitative or mixed-method approaches are also encouraged to gain deeper insights into the strategic motivations behind corporate environmental reporting.

Authors' Contributions

Indah Maulidiah is responsible for primary data collection, preliminary statistical analysis, and drafting the background section.

Linah Linah designed the research methodology, contributed to the literature review, and developed research instruments.

Morinda Silfiora conducted data analysis, wrote the discussion, and finalized the manuscript.

Ida Rosnidah provided overall academic supervision, guided research design, and reviewed and edited the entire manuscript.

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